

**SHAMOL ENERGIYASIDAN ELEKTR ENERGIYA OLUVCHI
QURILMALARNI STATISTIK TAHLILI.**

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada vertikal o'qli shamol turbinasi ko'rib chiqiladi, shuningdek, uning aerodinamik xususiyatlari. Shamol turbinasi parametrlari hisoblab chiqilgan va ular o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik va shamol generatorining samaradorligi.

Kalit so'zlar: Shamol turbinalari, shamol ehtimollik tahlili.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается ветродвигатель с вертикальной осью, а также его аэродинамические свойства. Рассчитаны параметры ветроустановки и зависимость между ними и КПД ветрогенератора.

Ключевые слова: PLC, скрытая марковская модель, вероятностный анализ.

Annotation. The article examines the vertical axis wind turbine, as well as its aerodynamic characteristics. The parameters of the wind turbine are calculated and the relationship between them and the efficiency of the wind generator.

Key words: PLC, Hidden Markov Model, Probabilistic Analysis.

Insoniyatning soni keskin o'sib bormoqda va bizning tabiiy resurslar katta yuk ostida. Talab ortib borayotganligi sababli, investitsiya qilish har qachongidan ham muhimroqdir qayta tiklanadigan energiya. Fotoalbom yoqilg'ilarni energiya sifatida iste'mol qilish, ekologik muammolarning asosiy sababi ekanligi aniqlandi. Fotoalbom yoqilg'i iste'molining yon mahsuloti karbonat angidriddir, bu global isishning asosiy sabablaridan biridir. Faoliyat natijasida hosil bo'lgan karbonat angidrid miqdori tashkilotlar, mahsulotlarni tashish, mahsulot ishlab chiqarish bo'yicha faoliyat, yoki inson faoliyati "uglerod izi" deb ataladi. Ommaviy axborot vositalari bu masalaga va ko'plab yashil harakatlarga e'tibor qaratdi uglerod izimizni kamaytirishga harakat qila boshladik. Karbonat angidrid hosil qilmaydigan bir nechta energiya turlari mavjud gaz. Bular yadroviy energiya va energiya kabi qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalari shamol, quyosh va suv. Qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalari eng toza, chunki chunki ular energiya ishlab chiqarish natijasida hosil bo'lgan chiqindilarni qoldirmaydi. Atom energiyasining yon mahsuloti radioaktiv chiqindilar, ularni qayta ishlash ular bo'lgunga qadar ko'p vaqt talab qilishi mumkin to'g'ri yo'q qilinadi.

1-rasm – Shamol energiyasidan foydalanish statistik natijalar.

Shamol turbinalarining ikkita asosiy turi mavjud: vertikal va gorizonta turlar. Gorizonta o'qli shamol turbinalari ilgari ixtiro qilingan va keng tarqalgan. 2-rasmda ushbu ikki turdagi diagramma ko'rsatilgan vertikal aylanish o'qi bo'lgan shamol generatorlari, bu ularning mashhurligiga olib keldi tizimi.

2-rasm – Shamol energiyasi bo'yicha ilmiy izlanishlay diagrammasi.

Shamol quyosh energiyasidan hosil bo'lib, erni notekis isitadi. Bu notekis isitish atmosferada bosimning o'zgarishini keltirib chiqaradi va shamolni yaratadi. Bu shamol shamol turbinalari tomonidan ishlatilishi mumkin. Shamol turbina pichoqlarini itarib yuboradi, milya o'qiga birlashtirilgan generator mexanik burilish energiyasini elektr energiyasiga aylantiradi, keyin uni iste'molchiga yuborish mumkin.

Shamol turbinalari energiya ishlab chiqarishning toza usulidir, ammo ular bir qator muhim kamchiliklarga ega. Bir muammo shundaki, ularni yig'ish va o'rnatish ancha qimmatga tushadi va shamol stansiyalari qishloqlar va shaharlar uchun etarli energiya ishlab chiqarish uchun joy talab qiladi. Yana bir muammo shundaki, ular shamol turbinalari narxini oqlash uchun elektr energiyasini ishlab chiqarish uchun

etarlicha kuchli shamol bo'lgan joylarda o'rnatilishi kerak.

Qadim zamonlardan beri shamol energiyasidan foydalanilgan. Avvalo, inson shamol energiyasi bilan harakatlanadigan yelkanli qayiq'larni yasashni o'rgandi. Qadimgi Forsda shamol g'ildiraklari donni maydalash uchun keng qo'llanilgan. Arab istilolaridan keyin bu texnologiya butun islom olamiga tarqaldi va hatto Xitoyga ham yetib bordi. Evropada shamol turbinalari 11-asrda paydo bo'lgan. Ikki asr o'tgach, ular Evropa mamlakatlari, ayniqsa Gollandiya hayotida muhim rol o'ynay boshladilar. Amerikada shamol turbinalari quduqlardan va arra tegirmonlarida suvni ko'tarish uchun g'arbiy hududlarni rivojlantirishda keng qo'llanilgan.

Birinchi bosqichda shamolning kinetik energiyasini shamol g'ildiragi milida mexanik energiyaga aylantirish uchun shamol turbinalari ishlatilgan, keyin esa ma'lum mexanizmlarni quvvat bilan ta'minlagan. Keyinchalik elektr energiyasi ishlab chiqarish uchun shamol turbinalari ishlatila boshlandi.

Shamolning o'zi bepul energiya bilan ta'minlansa-da, shamol turbinasi yaratish va ishlatish xarajatlari ishlab chiqarilgan elektr energiyasining narxi sezilarli bo'ladi. Suyuq organik yoqilg'i va tabiiy gazdan foydalanishning nisbatan arzon texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqish muqobil energiya manbalarini rivojlantirishni sekinlashtirdi. Ikkinchi jahon urushi oxirida neft narxining pastligi tufayli shamol energiyasiga qiziqish keskin pasaydi. Va faqat 1973 yilda, neft inqirozi boshlanganidan so'ng, shamol turbinalarini ishlab chiqish yana dunyoning ko'plab mamlakatlarida jadal amalga oshirila boshlandi. Rivojlanishlarning jadal rivojlanishiga davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanishi va soliq imtiyozlari turtki bo'ldi. To'plangan tajriba shamol fermalari deb ataladigan shamol turbinalari tomonidan ishlab chiqariladigan elektr energiyasining narxini besh baravar kamaytirishga imkon berdi. Shunday qilib, agar 1980 yil boshida shamol turbinalaridan olinadigan 1 kVt soat elektr energiyasining narxi, eng yaxshi holatda, taxminan 25 tsentni tashkil etgan bo'lsa, 1996 yilga kelib, eng qulay ish sharoitida u 5 tsentga tushdi. Shu bilan birga, shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, elektr energiyasining narxini smetasi qilingan taxminlarga va foydalanilgan hisoblash

modellariga bog'liq. 1 kVt soatning taxminiy narxi quyida keltirilgan bir qator omillar bilan belgilanadi:

1. Kapital xarajatlarning qiymati. Odatda ma'lum bir ko'rsatkich bilan tavsiflanadi - o'rnatilgan quvvatning 1 kVt narxi.

Bugungi kunda dunyodagi taxminan 1 dollar / kVtni tashkil qiladi. Shamol elektr stansiyalarini yaratish birlik xarajatlari qazib olinadigan yoqilg'ida ishlaydigan an'anaviy issiqlik elektr stansiyalari va gidroelektrostansiyalarning xarajatlari bilan taqqoslanadigan bo'ldi. Biroq, ikkinchisining o'rnatilgan quvvatdan foydalanish koeffitsienti kamida 50% ni tashkil qiladi, shamol turbinalari uchun quvvat koeffitsienti esa atigi 20% ni tashkil qiladi. Eslatib o'tamiz, quvvat koeffitsienti elektr stansiyasining normal ish sharoitida yiliga ishlab chiqaradigan elektr energiyasi miqdorining, agar stansiya o'rnatilgan quvvatda yil davomida uzluksiz ishlagan bo'lsa, erishish mumkin bo'lgan maksimal mumkin bo'lgan elektr energiyasini ishlab chiqarishga nisbatiga tengdir. Shamol turbinalari uchun quvvat koeffitsientining past qiymati shamol oqimlarining o'zgaruvchan intensivligi bilan bog'liq. Muayyan kapital xarajatlarni hisoblashda, odatda, tegishli foizlar bilan kredit shaklida bankdan olingan mablag'larning o'zlari tannarxini hisobga olish kerak. 1 kVt/soat ishlab chiqarilgan elektr energiyasi qiymati kreditlar, soliqlar va sug'urta chegirmalari va boshqalarni o'z ichiga olgan mablag'lar qiymatining o'zgarishiga juda sezgir.

2. Shamol turbinalari va gidroelektr stansiyalari uchun yoqilg'i narxi nolga teng.

3. Stansiyaning saqlash va ta'mirlash xarajatlari.

4. Elektr stansiyasini foydalanishdan chiqarish xarajatlari.

5. Stansiya o'rnatiladigan yerning narxi.

Ushbu omillarning ta'sirini hisobga olgan holda, ishlab chiqarilgan elektr energiyasining taxminiy qiymati sezilarli darajada farq qilishi mumkin va ma'lum darajada noaniq. Shunga qaramay, so'nggi 15-20 yil ichida ushbu xarajatlarning sezilarli darajada pasayishi aniq haqiqatdir.

Shunisi qiziqki, 1997 yildan buyon ba'zi mamlakatlarda shamol elektr

energiyasini sotish “yashil” narxlash sxemalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilib kelinmoqda. Atrof-muhitga g‘amxo‘rlik qiluvchi ongli xaridorlar elektr energiyasi uchun yuqori tariflarni to‘lashga tayyor va shu orqali o‘z hissalarini qo‘shadilar. ekologik toza energiya manbalarini rivojlantirishga.

1990-yillarda uglevodorod yoqilg‘isi narxlarining pasayishi shamol energetikasi rivojlanish sur‘atlarining biroz sekinlashishiga olib keldi. Biroq, yangi asrning boshlarida neft narxining yangi ko‘tarilishi ko‘plab mamlakatlarda ushbu sanoatga qiziqishning tez o‘shishiga sabab bo‘ldi.

Bugungi kunda shamol energetikasining jahon energetika balansiga qo‘shgan hissasi kichikligicha qolayotganiga qaramay, amalda uning an‘anaviy energiyaga nisbatan inkor etib bo‘lmaydigan afzalliklari, birinchi navbatda, quyidagi ko‘rsatkichlar bo‘yicha isbotlangan.

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